
UNFOLDING THE ASPECTS OF TECHNOLOGY LAW: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Social order became of utmost importance to man thus causing him to enter a social contract to abandon the vague obscurities of nature which did not provide for any sort of “rules”, “sanction”, or a “sovereign” to exist so as to navigate the daily affairs dealt by mankind. Entering this social contract facilitated man’s growth and provided better living conditions where the fear of sanction from the “sovereign” (i.e. the Government) induces him to act and conduct himself in a more civilized manner that aligns with the overall expectations of other people who just like him form a part of society by entering this social contract by the medium of “Laws” which become necessary for this arrangement to work. Regulation of human conduct has been seen through various facets of laws such as “Criminal laws”, “Family Laws”, “Company Laws”, “Contract Laws” etc. However, due to rapid advancements in the 21st century we have seen “Technology” being inculcated as an extremely necessary part of daily life which gives rise to the importance of developing a framework to regulate these technological advancements thus giving rise to the field of Technology Law. The Information Technology act, 2000 is the principal statute regulating the use of Technology devices and how such devices are to be properly used but with recent and more advancements in Technology with the onset of Drones, NFT’s, AI, Blockchain, Cryptocurrency and other such advancements have led to this act being insufficient and not very exhaustive with regards to these fields thus calling upon the need of a new legislation so as to address these advancements.

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I. Facets of Technology Law and its Intersection with Human Rights

Technology Law as we know it today covers an array of topics such as IPR (Intellectual Property Rights), Fintech Industries, Data Protection, Technology contracts, AI, Drones etc.

Before delving into these facets of Tech Law we must also acknowledge how this field has a relevant intersection with the realm of Human rights specifically in the Indian context.

The recent passing of the new Criminal laws in India specifically the BNSS, 2023 can be taken an example to closely understand this intersection of Technology Law with Human rights as the Search and Seizure laws under Section 94 has enlarged the scope of search and seizure of documents by the police by now expanding the scope of this search and seizure to include any document and “Electronic communication devices” which is likely to contain digital evidence of some sort relevant to the investigation of that particular case and this section read with the Information Technology act, 2000 leads us to the interpretation of how “Cell phones” and other such electronic devices and communications such as “WhatsApp chats”, electronic images, financial transactions history and social media accounts can be summoned by the IO of a case via a written order for the purpose of corroborating the facts of a case.

The High court of Karnataka has also given its ruling in the case of *Virendra Khanna vs State of Karnataka WP No. 11759/2020* solidifying that once the IO has access to a person’s smartphone, electronic equipment or email account he would have complete access to the data contained in such a device and conferred the responsibility on the IO of the case to protect the accused’s data with regards to personal and private information that are irrelevant to the case.

Further the courts also emphasized in the same case for a need of establishing new guidelines while conducting such searches and the same was put forth in the Landmark case of *Ram Ramaswamy vs UOI* where 5 important rules were established while conducting searches to protect the individual's right to privacy and life with liberty under article 21 of the Indian Constitution where the need for filtering private information and information relevant to the case was given importance along with mentioning how it was important to not compel a person to give out such a device’s password using forceful means and also set a time limit of 30 days within which the “independent authority” investigating the case effaced from the influence of the

police must return the taken device thus upholding an Individual's Integrity and keeping in line with Article 21 and Article 20(3) of the Indian constitution.

II. Intellectual Property Rights

Unlike Immoveable and Moveable properties that are tangible IPR or Intellectual Property Rights refers to a bunch of rights given to a person in lieu of his/her creations/inventions which particularly are rights meant to protect the use of such inventions by other 3rd parties for a specific period of time² for which such a creator is issued a patent once he/ she applies for the same. IPR applies to an array of inventions and creations under its ambit of which some include artwork made by artists, Songs made by Musicians, Breakthroughs made by R&D teams, Discoveries made by Scientists and discovery of new pharmaceutical drugs etc.

IPR itself does not only contain the right to patent one's work but consists of several rights for the benefit of the creator such as Copyrights, Patents, Trademarks, Geographical designs and Industrial designs. Patents are IP rights granted for a technical innovation made by a person and according to Section 3 of the Indian Patents act, 1970 a patent cannot be frivolous in nature, it cannot be an invention against natural laws, inventions detrimental to animal, plant and even human life³. This patent in return grants exclusive rights to its owner to utilize his creation without any third party using the same creation for the purpose of making profits or monetary gains unless permission is granted by the patent holder. Trademarks are governed by the Indian Trademarks act 1999 refers to a name, slogan, symbol or even a drawing that is unique and distinctive to a business which cannot be used by other businesses from using the same. Trademarks generally help businesses brand themselves and gain customer traction as a unique and independent goods or service provider thus building their own reputation, further the trademarks act provides for a trademark to be renewed from time to time and every initial or first trademark last for 10 years this is done to limit unnecessary registered trademarks that would have no application.

² Chandra Nath Saha and Sanjib Bhattacharya, 'Intellectual Property Rights: An Overview and Implications in Pharmaceutical Industry' (2011) 3(1) *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology & Research* 88 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3217699/> accessed 9 December 2024

³ Lalit Jajpura, Bhupinder Singh, and Rajkishore Nayak, 'An Introduction to Intellectual Property Rights and their Importance in Indian Context' (2017) 22 *J Intellectual Property Rights* 32.

Similarly, copyrights are rights issued to creators of music, art and similar works where exclusive rights to use such content is given to the inventor of such works. The Indian Copyright act 1957 governs copyrights and unlike patents there is no requirement for registration of a copyright as the same right is granted as soon as a creation is produced however, it is always better to get a registration of a copyright so as to establish evidence in case any dispute with regards to an invention rises. For works such as art, music and other types of literary works in India a Copyright exist for a period of 60 years after the death of the creator thus providing lifelong and extensive benefits to the holder in form of royalties.

III. Importance of IP in businesses over the past decades

IP has become a tool for businesses across the globe for the purpose of debt financing. All Intangible assets of a business including its IP and Goodwill had reached 74 trillion Dollars in the year 2021⁴ the importance of IP can be seen with the process and trend of securitization of IP assets by employing IP assets to function as collateral. Large banking institutions across the globe such as Morgan Stanley, JP Morgan Chase, Bank of America and Wells Fargo have accepted IP assets as collateral from companies and have facilitated various transactions. In the Indian scenario the technology, semiconductor and pharmaceutical industries have utilized IP based financing however the national IPR policy of 2016 which aimed towards facilitating the securitization of IP assets has failed to inculcate various changes and we look towards the SARAFESI act 2002, Section 2(z) for the process of securitization. This conversion of IP into marketable securities had also been suggested by WIPO or the World Intellectual Property Organization that later gained immense traction by banks in the year 2011 further UNCITRAL (United Nations Commission on International Trade Law) has introduced a legislative guide on the process of IP securitization⁵ and various countries are progressing faster in this field as compared to India due to the amateur 2016 national IPR policy that is still inadequate in addressing the issue of securitization. The essentials a business must have for treating IP assets

⁴ Nirupam Lodha, Malika Nandkeolyar, and Vanshika Thapliyal, 'Unlocking Financing Potential of IP: The Role of IP Securitization' (Khaitan & Co) <https://www.khaitanco.com/> accessed 10 December 2024.

⁵The Role of IP Securitization' <https://lexindis.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/SECURITIZATION-OF-INTELLECTUAL-PROPERTY> accessed 10 December 2024.

as collateral is to check the future cash flows of the company from such assets and assess whether these cash flows are sufficient for the purpose of securitization.

In the case of *Canara Bank vs NG Subbaraya Setty*⁶ the courts did not treat the IP as a security due to the fact that the Setty had not pledged his asset (in the case which was a trademark by the name of “EENADU”) as a security for the purpose of seeking credit in form of a loan from Canara Bank and thus holding that the asset could not be treated as a security for the purpose of Section 6 of the Banking Regulation act, 1949. which leads to the interpretation that an independent IP itself cannot be treated as a security unless it is expressly used for the purpose of securing credit in the form of a security.

Thus, with rapid increase in valuation of IP assets it becomes crucial to adopt and inculcate a system that acknowledges IP assets as securities to facilitate financial transactions that would help businesses thrive in a flexible market and give meaning to the diverse IP portfolios held by companies.

IV. Fintech and its development in India

The word “Fintech” is simply a combination of the words “Financial” and “Technology” that refer to an integration of these forementioned terms where financial services are provided to individuals by using latest technological advancements. From basic services such as making online transactions by using services such as “RuPay”, “Paytm”, “PhonPe” etc. To providing options in Blockchain, Cryptocurrency, NFT’s that are services which are on the contrary considered to be more “unorthodox” financial activities come under the ambit of the “Fintech” sector.

The RBI has attempted to regulate and recognize the boom in the IT sector that led to the creation of “Fintech markets” that was made out as a sector of finance different than traditional financial markets. The initial attempts of the RBI included the introduction of the Payment Settlement Systems act, 2007 or the PSSA that acknowledges and lays out the accepted and

⁶ Yashvi, 'IP As Security (Canara Bank v NG Subbaraya Setty)' (Mondaq, 24 July 2018)

<https://www.mondaq.com/india/trade-secrets/715820/ip-as-security-canara-bank-v-ng-subbaraya-setty> accessed 10 December 2024.

legitimate systems of making payments and settlements some which are UPI, E wallet, and other means of digital transactions and further specifies how corporations attempting to operate such systems require RBI's authorization⁷ which in turn led to various NBFC's seeking registration to do the same. Further due to the increase in the number of such NBFC's who now could operate these payments systems the NPCI was created and the RuPay card network was established that led to a major switch towards digitized payments thus diverting from traditional payment methods in India.

These developments further led to the impact of Fintech industries reach a global stage where gateway regulations were established in 2015 for the sole purpose of facilitating online payments occurring across other territories in the form of imports and exports. The RBI has done an effective job to centralize the entire payment system with respect to the establishment of the new payment systems and along the Ministry of Finance governs such transactions.

V. Navigating unorthodox payment systems and the rise of cryptocurrency

Coming to a more complex form of payment that has arisen as a result of the Fintech sector rise, the RBI had initially banned financial institutions and Fintech companies from dealing with cryptocurrency in 2018 via a circular. The RBI further wished to introduce CBCD's instead of crypto assets with the aim of attempting to centralize and create a framework regulating crypto transfers along the aim of banning crypto mining, holding, transfers etc. Via a Crypto ban/regulation bill. However recent trends have been developed in the year 2020, March as it was at this time when the Supreme Court decided to unban the usage of crypto currency in India by considering the circular banning crypto currency as contravening article 19 1 (g) of the Indian constitutional guarantee of Freedom of carrying out any trade which is a fundamental guarantee under part 3⁸ of the Indian constitution In the case of *Mobile Association of India vs RBI, 2020* recently we have seen that the courts have gone so far as to even suggest crypto to be a "parallel economy": that needs regulations adopted into a framework and has acknowledged the use of

⁷ Srinath Dasari, Vipul Jain, and Rachana Rautray, 'Fintech Laws and Regulations, 2021, Fifth Edition' (AZB & Partners, 21 June 2021) <https://www.azbpartners.com/bank/fintech-laws-and-regulations-2021-fifth-edition/> accessed 10 December 2024.

⁸ Ahlawat & Associates, 'The Legal Aspects of Cryptocurrency in India' (Ahlawat & Associates, 8 December 2020) <https://www.ahlawatassociates.com/blog/legal-aspects-of-cryptocurrency-in-india> accessed 10 December 2024

crypto in the future in the case of *Shailesh Babulal Bhatt vs State of Gujarat and Anr.* Where the courts observed that the 30% tax imposed on crypto profits under Section 115 BBH of the Income tax act, implies the Indian government in recognizing it to be a financial asset thus turning a blind eye in the future towards the same would lead to us turning a blind eye towards the ground reality i.e. (crypto's existence being used internationally for making transactions) thus requiring commercial wisdom to be applied by experts to help suggest regulations apt for the purpose of safely navigating our way around this mechanism. Till date the crypto debate has been a gray area as the validity of cryptocurrency in India is left as an open question as the Crypto regulation bill has not been passed by the parliament and crypto is treated as a "Virtual Digital Asset" under Section 2 clause 47 A of the Income tax act and is still not recognized as legal tender for the purpose of daily transactions however holding and trading of such assets is made permissible post the ban.

The unbanning of crypto has now led to a significant rise in the Fintech sector and large number of people have invested money in crypto currency through various platforms such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Dogecoin etc. As a result of which in 2021 the Companies Act, 2013 has now been amended to make it mandatory for companies to disclose their investments in cryptocurrencies at the beginning of each financial year thus paving way for the growth and recognition of cryptocurrencies as part of the company's balance sheet. The unbanning of cryptocurrencies has further paved the way for individual investors to involve themselves into cryptocurrencies and hold such assets thus leading to a possible growth of crypto in the future with the applied use of blockchain that acts as a medium for recording these types of transactions. The MeitY in March 2023 announced repealing the IT act, 2000 with the new Digital India Act that is expected to address AI, Internet and even Blockchain related issues.

With regards to Blockchain the Indian government is now attempting to find innovative techniques to implement the same for which the MeitY has released the "National Strategy on Blockchain" in 2021.⁹ Here the government plans on establishing a framework related to blockchain that could help in various sectors including E voting, finance and possibly become a

⁹ Prateek Tripathi, 'The Growing Role of Blockchain in Indian Governance' (Observer Research Foundation, 8 December 2024) <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-growing-role-of-blockchain-in-indian-governance>

way of digitized governance of such sectors. The Government of Tamil Nadu has envisaged for a more radical implementation of blockchain with their concept of *Nambikkai Inaiyam*¹⁰ where the idea is to integrate blockchain services with the functioning of both public and private sectors with its effect on G2C and G2G products ensuring transparency in the regulatory framework over such services including filing of online taxes, making online payments etc. By using the hash encrypted ledger that ensures the legitimacy on account of online transactions by showing the amount transacted, the time and date of the transaction and can facilitate in ensuring accountability by curbing faults such as lack of accessibility as this feature enables zero down time which is helpful for older platforms (i.e. legacy platforms) to function smoothly who are unable to compete with current cloud computed softwares. Further they also envisage on making payment gateways thus attempting to include a variety of options available for making transactions

Blockchain was being used specifically for the purpose of cryptocurrency related transactions which were not looked upon in a good light by the RBI however with the onset of platforms like Ethereum we realize that this system can be used for performing a variety of tasks i.e. self-governance. More recently Blockchain has also been viewed in a positive light with regards to its applicability in keeping property records where the use of Non fungible Token's popularly referred to as NFT's have been used by the Kolkata Development authorities that covers 27,000 acres of land.¹¹

Further, 50,000 NFT's have been used that showcase a million property records which are free from being fraudulent on account this inbuilt mechanism contained within blockchain thus not leaving any room for doubt with respect to the legitimacy of such records.

VI. Data Protection and Privacy

Another fascinating yet essential facet of technology law is Data protection and privacy where data privacy refers to the extent of autonomy a person has over his own data with respect to the

¹⁰ Tamil Nadu e-Governance Agency, 'e-Governance Policies' (TNeGA) <https://tnega.tn.gov.in/page/36> accessed 21 May 2025.

¹¹ Prateek Tripathi, 'The Growing Role of Blockchain in Indian Governance' (Observer Research Foundation, 8 December 2024) <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-growing-role-of-blockchain-in-indian-governance>

same not being misused or there being any sort of unwanted interference by a 3rd party over an individual's data. Thus, to secure a person's right to privacy which is a facet of right to life and personal liberty under article 21 of the Indian Constitution has become extremely important in today's times with the growth in technology that allows a possibility of manipulation of personal data by 3rd parties for which regulations need to be established.

VII. Recent development in Data privacy and the DPDP Act, 2023

Protection of digital data via regulations has become necessary with the onset of technological advancements for which the Digital Personal Data Protection act, 2023 had recently been legislated. The catalyst for introducing regulations related to digital data protection was the case of *K.S Puttaswamy v. UOI* where the judges held that Right to life and liberty under Article 21 of the Indian constitution was to include "Right to privacy" under its ambit and later on the Government of India along with the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (**MeitY**) passed the Digital Personal Data Protection bill in the year 2022¹².

Recently in 2023 the forementioned bill was passed and became an act and under its scope it considers only personal data collected in a digital space or data collected in a non-digitized form but then converted to digital form thus only extending to personal data stored or being converted to digital form and doesn't include personal non digital data. Rule 2 clarifies the applicability of the Act to processing both within India and extraterritorially if such processing relates to offering goods or services to Indian residents. While this aligns with global standards (e.g., GDPR), enforcement mechanisms for foreign entities remain unclear, particularly in cases where the Data Protection Board lacks jurisdictional reach there are still uncertainties about various propositions in the draft rules that are highlighted below.

1. Consent and Notice (Rule 3): - The Draft Rules reinforce a consent-centric model of data protection. Data fiduciaries must seek explicit consent via clear notices, available in English and other official Indian languages. The inclusion of multilingual notices, while commendable, poses logistical issues. It demands both translation fidelity and digital infrastructure to deliver these notices efficiently.

¹² DLA Piper, 'Data Protection Laws of the World: India' (DLA Piper) <https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=IN> accessed 10 December 2024.

A key point of analysis: consent fatigue. By requiring granular consent across multiple languages and interfaces, the model risks becoming performative. It is essential to consider default opt-out systems and simplified notices to ensure meaningful consent, rather than ritualistic compliance.

2. Consent Managers, A New Regulatory Actor Rule 4: - Presents the concept of registered "Consent Managers" — intermediaries who allow Data Principals to manage, review, and withdraw consent. Conceptually, this introduces accountability and user control. However, operationalizing these platforms with neutrality and privacy-by-design remains a massive regulatory challenge.

The Rules remain vague about data liability in cases of misuse by Consent Managers. Should they be treated as co-fiduciaries? Further jurisprudential clarification is needed.

3. Significant Data Fiduciaries (SDFs) Rule 12: - SDFs are fiduciaries who, due to scale or sensitivity of data, are subject to enhanced obligations:

- Annual Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs)
- Independent audits
- Algorithmic accountability checks

While these obligations hint towards maturity in India's regulatory vision, the rules are ambiguous. For instance, they do not define clear standards for determining algorithmic "risk" or methodology for algorithm auditing thus possibly only creating a facade of "transparency" in absence of such guidelines. The lack of protocol risks rendering these requirements symbolic.

Moreover, localization mandates are hinted at but not fully elaborated. This introduces uncertainty for global companies who must now potentially localize entire infrastructure stacks without clarity on enforcement or scope.

4. Children and Persons with Disabilities: Rule 10: - The Draft Rules require verifiable consent from guardians for processing children's data. Multiple pathways are provided, including digital tokens, prior records, and Digi locker IDs. While inspired by GDPR's Article 8, the Indian model lacks standardization.

Further complexity arises in the Fourth Schedule's exemptions. Certain data fiduciaries, such as healthcare institutions, are exempted under specific conditions. However, these carve-outs are narrowly defined and create operational confusion for platforms serving mixed user bases (e.g., ed-tech platforms).

5. Breach Notification and Incident Reporting (Rule 7): - Rule 7 demands breach reporting to the Data Protection Board and affected Data Principals within 72 hours¹³. This diverges from GDPR's risk-based notification threshold. While well-intentioned, the rule increases compliance burden without distinguishing between low-impact and critical breaches.

Notably, the Rules mandate separate reports to CERT-IN and sectoral regulators, creating a multi-faceted reporting obligation. This could result in conflicting guidance or delays in action.

6. Data Retention and Erasure A new compliance burden arises from the mandate to erase personal data after the end of its specified purpose. Major platforms (social media, e-commerce, gaming) with user bases exceeding 20 million must delete data after 3 years of inactivity, post a 48-hour re-engagement window.¹⁴

While framed as a privacy safeguard, this rule risks disrupting business continuity and user experience. For instance, dormant accounts may hold digital assets or records critical to legal and financial claims.

VIII. Gaming Laws

Understanding gaming laws involves indulging in the world of casinos, wagering, gambling and betting where players make such wagers with the intention of possibly winning these bets for which they receive direct monetary rewards. However, the legitimacy of such games comes into question due to a variety of such games being based on the premises of pure "luck" that include games like Poker, roulette, lotteries, craps etc. Where the player has little to no chance of predicting the outcome of such a game as compared to other games where the player uses his own skills to predict an outcome such as horse riding as was decided by the Supreme court in K.R Lakshmanan's case for which they stated that such games involve mental effort on behalf of the player by analyzing the condition of the horse, the race track, the past performance of the horse on the basis of which they make such decisions thus making it possible to predict the outcome of the race after a thorough analysis and the question of protecting people addicted to

¹³ Luthra and Luthra Law Offices India, 'Update on the Digital Personal Data Protection Rules, 2025' (Luthra and Luthra, 3 January 2025) <https://luthra.com/update-on-the-digital-personal-data-protection-rules-2025> accessed 21 May 2025.

¹⁴ Nishith Desai Associates, 'India's Draft Digital Personal Data Protection Rules, 2025 – The Next Step Towards Operationalising the DPDP Act' (Nishith Desai Associates, 4 January 2025) <https://www.nishithdesai.com/generateHTML/15226/4> accessed 21 May 2025.

such games becomes important as various people get into major debt due to such games being unregulated and against their interests due to no official rules being put in place.

The act that controls such games was established in 1867 by the Centre and is referred to as the Public Gambling act, however due to such a legislation being passed centuries ago it becomes outdated and fails to address the question of gambling as it only accounts for such gaming activities in "playing houses" that are physically located in places in India and completely neglects virtual gaming platforms being devised for the same which include sites like Stake.com, 1XBET, Pari Match etc. Further casinos in specifically in Goa have been established on "water" to curb the effects of the 1867 act that doesn't account for gambling activities being conducted on water bodies.

IX. Changes in Gaming Laws and its criticism

The new IT rules passed in 2021 were amended recently in 2023 by **MeitY** so as to include online games and protection of players operating these platforms. However, the economic survey 2020-21 also shows how the government has failed to keep up with the technological advancements via their legislations and the same statement can be applied for online gaming activities¹⁵.

Rule 2(qa) of these new rules defines an online game as "a game that is offered on the Internet and is accessible by a user through a computer resource if he deposits with the expectation of earning winnings" however this definition fails to account for free games that contain some sort of subscription within them thus causing ambiguity as the payment for the purpose of such a game can be a possibility in the future stages.

Further rule 2 (qd) of the new rules includes non-monetary exchanges in the meaning of "winnings" and "deposits" which leads to the interpretation that these rules govern games where there is no involvement of actual money.

¹⁵ Anay Mehrotra and Puneet Srivastava, 'Online Gaming Platforms and Self-Regulation: Exploring the Feasibility of the Mechanism' (Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy, 5 July 2023) <https://vidhilegalpolicy.in/blog/online-gaming-platforms-and-self-regulation/> accessed 10 December 2024

Further with the boom in technology there has been a rise in the E sports industry where various players come together and form and compete with other teams playing these games for the purpose of getting a cash prize. The question of whether these cash prizes fall within the ambit of the act is also unclear thus proving to be an impediment in the field of this industry as the E sports industry involves participating in games and events that do not involve gambling or betting and pure involves games of skill such as Call of Duty, CS:GO, Fortnite etc. Which cannot be considered as illegal as the case of *RMD Chamarbaugwala vs UOI* cleared the fact that games of skill could not be considered as illegal for the purpose of being considered as “gambling”.

Thus, it is clear to say that the government needs to provide clarity with respect to its legislations on such matters and remove ambiguities that have traverse effects on people who may not even be involved in such matters thus making the use of such legislation to be *Ultra Vires* its power.

X. Cyber laws

Cyber laws are the laws that govern the general daily uses of computer networks, services, online internet platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram etc. And even governing crimes committed on such platforms in forms of leaking personal information, blackmailing done using these platforms, Hacking into a personal account etc. Which constitute what we know today as cybercrimes. Along with the primary legislation that lays down the framework for these laws known as the IT act, 2000 there has been a necessary intersection of the right to privacy with these laws thus giving further importance to also consider the DPDP act, 2023.

The IT act addresses issues of hacking and imposes sanctions for the same under Section 66 for a period of 3 years in jail and imposes fines for the same. Further under Section 66C punishment for fraudulently using another person's identity by fraudulent use of a person's signatures for the purpose of intentionally misleading someone is covered under this act. Further the highest degree of punishment for such crimes can be seen in form of cyber terrorism under section 66 F of the act that lays down life imprisonment for the same and refers to a scenario where online platforms are misused for the purpose of threatening the sovereignty of the nation and includes contaminating important government systems with viruses or intentionally and illegally gains

access to protected and classified information unavailable to the general public for the purpose of their security.

Further the MeitY has also established the CERT-IN which is nothing but an emergency response team in reaction to cybercrimes and performs other functions to help the public in such matters and is established under the IT act, 2000 itself.

Some of the functions of CERT-IN involve spreading and collecting information about cyber related incidents and even issuing guidelines regarding safe cyber practices. CERT directions apply to VPN service providers, cloud service providers, virtual exchange currency providers etc.¹⁶ these directions involve such service providers to disclose certain specified cyber incidents within 6 hours of such occurrence and such an obligation to do so is mandatory and if not done can cause punishment up to 1 year in jail or a fine of 1 Lakh Rupees.

Further such providers need to establish Points of contact or POC's where they can establish contact with CERT-IN along with mandatory need for maintaining logs for a period of up to 180 days after which they need to share the same with CERT-IN

XI. Cyber Crimes in India

India has lost over 18 billion US dollars because of cybercrimes and in 2018 27,000 cases were reported that were regarding cybercrimes¹⁷ that grew rapidly on the onset of the 90s with regards to increasing growth in technology. Maharashtra, Pune and Mumbai have become a frequent target to these crimes in lieu of their increasing population and use of the Internet which makes them more vulnerable to being exploited to such crimes. An instance of this could be seen in Pune in the year 2018 in August when the Cosmos Bank cyber-attack occurred where sophisticated techniques and use of malware to hack in the bank 's system led to a huge financial crisis for the people associated with the bank as huge amounts of unwanted and unintentional transactions took place from people's accounts without their knowledge and further this incident

¹⁶ AZB & Partners, 'CERT-In Directions' (AZB & Partners, 18 May 2022) <https://www.azbpartners.com/bank/cert-in-directions/> accessed 10 December 2024.

¹⁷ Nidhi Narnolia, 'Cyber Crime in India: An Overview' (Legal Service India) <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-4998-cyber-crime-in-india-an-overview.html> accessed 10 December 2024

lead to the rise in the growing importance of maintenance of records and constant monitoring of such systems in order to reduce the risk of such attacks becoming frequent occurrences.

Further in 2016 when demonetization was introduced in India which devalued the use of high currency notes of namely the 500 rupee and 1000 rupee note. Various cybercriminals manipulated people and misled them into believing that it was important to pursue cyber safety and measures in such times when the currency was devalued for the purpose of fighting counterfeit and illegally held currency and secured personal information and data from people on such a pretext in order to conduct their malicious scams.

XII. Telemedia communications

Media and entertainment pose to be extremely important to Indian consumers in the market as can be drawn from the booming of this sector by 11.5 % in 2023 and reach 29.2 billion US \$¹⁸. People consume all types of shows in India and that includes shows in different languages being translated and includes other types of online media including movies, podcasts, songs etc. Thus, making India one of the largest markets for the consumption of such services that have a global impact due to the diversity of media and entertainment being adopted.

The technological advancements that have led to the ease of access to the internet and the replacement of BSNL by Airtel providing faster services, the onset of 5G and even the low rates at which data services are provided by service providers across India working for different companies thus giving consumers an array of options to choose from are some of the major factors that have contributed towards the growth of the Telecommunications and media industry. Streaming devices have increased in number such as Netflix, Amazon Prime, Hotstar etc. And with the options of OTT platforms the number of options for consumers has increased immensely.

The telecommunications sector involves providing services as the name suggests for communication between people through technological devices across different countries and can extend communication to over various distances by using artificial satellites broadband services

¹⁸ Benjamin E Marks (ed), *Lexology Panoramic: Media and Entertainment Law, Edition 5 – India* (Weil Gotshal & Manges LLP 2024) <https://www.khaitanco.com/sites/default/files/2024-01/Lexology%20Panoramic%20-%20Media%20and%20Entertainment%20Law%20-%20Edition%205%20-%20India.pdf>

and provide network coverage for the same. The latest trend in this sector comes with introduction of the 5G network which ensures stronger connectivity over large distances, ensures large area of network coverage and reduces the amount of connectivity issues which can also help business meetings and calls taking place between two territorially distinct companies.

The possibility of such innovative solutions for global communications is possible due to the technological advancements made in recent times which other than building of software's, optical fibers and producing cloud computation the tech industry also now gives us the opportunity to use AI (Artificial Intelligence) as means to improve our understanding of this sector and introduce machine learning to fix adapt and improve one's way of performing tasks in this sector in more efficient and lesser time consuming manner.

XIII. Regulations and issues of privacy in the Telecom sector

Earlier the Indian Telegraph act, Telegraph wires unlawful possession act and the wireless telegraphy act had jurisdiction with respect to matters regarding telecommunication however recently the Telecommunications act, 2023 has been passed which now supersedes all these laws.

Apart from legislative statutes the TDSAT and the TRAI are also present to address the disputes in this sector. TRAI authorities are required to make sure that messages made on communication platforms such as WhatsApp are end to end encrypted which is a measure taken to protect the privacy of individuals who might potentially share personal data and information through such platforms which can allow possibilities of such data being misused or leaked against the interest of the users using this platform.

This act has allowed the government to intercept messages thus allowing there a scope for invasion of privacy but only after establishing that there is a sort of "practical reasonableness" to do so and this challenge whether or not the government can do the same was upheld after surviving judicial review in the case of *People's Union of Civil Liberties v. Union of India*, (2003) 2 SCR 1136¹⁹. This invasion of privacy can be done by the government only after establishing that the same is being done keeping in mind a reasonable concern for public safety. Thus,

¹⁹ Arun Prabhu and Anoushka Soni, 'The Telecommunications Act, 2023' (Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas, 23 January 2024) https://corporate.cyrilamarchandblogs.com/2024/01/the-indian-telecommunications-bill-2023/#_ftnref34

imposing reasonable restrictions to the right to privacy as being extended under article 21 according to the Putaswamy case.

Under this act the licensing required by service providers and other various processes to go through regarding registrations and compliance with general rules has now been dismantled as the TSP or telecom service providers and other entities possessing radio services and devices will now fall under the jurisdiction this new Telecommunications act, 2023.

Further service providers must also act according to the DPDP act, 2023 where they have an obligation to safeguard the personal information of data principles where the exceptional standard applies to minor's data where the consent of their guardian must be taken before processing the same in accordance with the DPDP act, 2023 that derives the same from Article 8 of the GDPR and CCPA rules.

XIV. AI, Blockchain and the way forward

With technology being advanced with the help of AI the government needs to adapt and develop frameworks adopting AI which has not been completely done by now. The issue that arises here is the constantly changing and growing AI where making regulations regarding the same becomes extremely tough for legislators who would now be expected to be up to date with regards to these changes and develop frameworks for the same.

The MeitY in March 2023 announced repealing the IT act, 2000 with the new Digital India Act that is expected to address AI, Internet and even Blockchain related issues.

With regards to Blockchain the Indian government post the unbanning of crypto is now attempting to find innovative techniques to implement the same for which the MeitY has released the "National Strategy on Blockchain" in 2021.²⁰ Here the government plans on establishing a framework related to blockchain that could help in various sectors including E voting, finance and possibly become a way of digitized governance of such sectors.

²⁰ Prateek Tripathi, 'The Growing Role of Blockchain in Indian Governance' (Observer Research Foundation, 8 December 2024) <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-growing-role-of-blockchain-in-indian-governance>

Blockchain refers to nothing but a digitized bookkeeping mechanism with regards to various types of transactions which are stored on a computer and isn't centralized (i.e. involves no aspect of the government). Once this transaction occurs the same is stored in this book which forms a block and several of these blocks are connected to each other via a timestamp indicating when the transaction occurred called a "hash" which in turn connects these blocks and forms the Blockchain. The most interesting part about this process is that for a block to be amalgamated with corresponding blocks the nodes of this entire system allow whether the block in question can be a part of the previous blockchain or not and this ensures a form of self-governance which becomes extremely attractive to the government if they understand how to tap the potential from such an Idea to convert into something be used in daily scenarios.

Blockchain was being used specifically for the purpose of cryptocurrency related transactions which were not looked upon in a good light by the RBI however with the onset of platforms like Ethereum we realize that this system can be used for performing a variety of tasks that is of self-governance. More recently Blockchain has also been viewed in a positive light with regards to its applicability in keeping property records where the use of Non fungible Token's popularly referred to as NFT's have been used by the Kolkata Development authorities that covers 27,000 acres of land.²¹

Further 50,000 NFT's have been used that showcase a million property records which are free from being malicious records due to this inbuilt mechanism contained within blockchain thus not leaving any room for doubt with respect to the legitimacy of such records.

XV. Conclusion

Technology law contains within itself an array of diversified topics that have important usages and requirements in the present and the near future and developing frameworks with respect to these fields is the way to get ahead in these sectors.

Technology law thus does not only refer to aspects regarding the mechanical or scientific functioning of the world but also includes extremely important aspects of human rights and

²¹ Prateek Tripathi, 'The Growing Role of Blockchain in Indian Governance' (Observer Research Foundation, 8 December 2024) <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/the-growing-role-of-blockchain-in-indian-governance>

rights that have severe consequences if not addressed by developing such frameworks and establishing regulations.

